

A Study on the Impact of Motivation on the Employee Productivity of Janata Bank in Bangladesh

Md. Amran Hossain^{1*}, Shek Aziz Muhammad Shati², Bandara Wanninayake³

^{1,3}University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka

²National University, Bangladesh

Abstract: Representatives are an organization's occupation. How they feel about the function they are doing and the outcomes got from that work straightforwardly affect an association's execution and, at last, its solidness. An insecure association at last fails to meet expectations. The review had the accompanying destinations: to set up the connection amongst inspiration and higher efficiency among laborers, to discover any connection between motivational elements and work of staff and to decide how impetuses impact specialist's way to deal with work and their execution. To accomplish these objectives, a survey was outlined in view of the goals. The finished surveys were prepared and broke down utilizing the Simple Percentage and Chi-Square. The discoveries of this review uncovered that nearby fiscal motivators, another key consider persuading representatives is to include them in the process went for accomplishing authoritative adequacy on the grounds that without their co-operation and bolster a lot of administrative vitality might be squandered. The review presumed that endeavors ought to be gone for inspiring staff of all levels with a specific end goal to expand efficiency for higher returns. The examination made broad utilization of both essential and optional information. Essential information was acquired by regulating an all-around organized poll to respondents in the chose bank. Meetings were likewise led from the bank to get to the data on motivator bundle by the bank. Janata Bank reports, the Internet, magazines, exchange diaries, were gathered for the review. This review uncovered that the specialist's motivational procedures in Janata Bank have experienced enormous change since the association was built up.

Keywords: Motivation, Employee, Productivity, Performance, Bank, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Laborer inspiration is specifically connected to worker responsibility, faculty profitability and exchange picks up, office resembles a delightful sparkling auto and their staff is a top-of-the-line motor yet auto (association) is worthless without powerful motor (staff). The satisfactory workers are always in excessive demand, and will change businesses if they are not saved influenced at work, according to April, 2009 and 2023, Article in Bloomberg business week. Employers appreciate that they have got to furnish a work environment that creates motivation in men and women. However numerous businesses neglect to completely get a handle on the criticalness of

inspiration in participating in their central goal and creative and insightful. There are two normal strategies to encourage a worker. One is via extrinsic motivation or material pleasure, and the opposite is via intrinsic motivation or delivering intangible or psychological rewards for instance: - say "thanks", "best Job", or "well executed" to exhibit admire sort for tough and just right work.

Regarding life, what to think about it supported is quite a bit of a man or lady's choice. The inspiration clarifications that men and ladies feel, make them to be empowered, and are basically not the inspiration. Organizations have needed to lease motivational speakers who are intended to propel the staff however then this ends up being, to a certain extent, a misuse of money and resources. The motivational sound framework and the motivational talks should, no longer essentially rouse the staff, however on the other hand to enable the workers to be more gainful of their occupations (Johnson and Geupel 2010, p. 139). Indistinguishable to Chris Anderson who was advantageous plentiful to cite the expressions of a French Economist who passes by method for the title Jean – Baptiste (1767 – 1832) as noted by means of Mancini (2012, p. 6) articulating that give that is effortlessly accessible, creates in itself, its own request.

Considering that an ever-increasing number of people feel that for them to be incited, they require inconceivably famous motivational sound framework, then the "Motivational speakers" continue rising up out of left, right and focus in all edges of the part. Goodness, beyond any doubt! A genuine smooth business plausibility in reality. A few people do have a high vibe of self – inspiration while others must be given a start key for them to end up affected.

A person's inside inspiration is the thing that drives this kind of individual into getting up each and every single morning and look forward to one brighter day. It's for all intents and purposes incredible for one to pronounce that they don't appear to be incited seeing that, inspiration does not doubtlessly, depend upon the accomplishments. In any case, profitability (Johnson and Geupel, 2009, p. 138 +) can routinely be ascribed to reality that inspiration has played a fundamental position in ensuring

*Corresponding author: amranhossain36@gmail.com

that there's broadened execution (Shadare and Hammed, 2010, p. 8). The undeniable reality that one has woken up from sleeping pad and accomplishes something is sufficient inspiration. The one distinction is that there are exceptional levels of inspiration. Some have inordinate inspiration to do what they're slanted and skilled to do, even as to others, the incitement is to do as a considerable measure as the base prerequisites. One of the essential chronicled colloquialisms as referred to in Levy (2011, p. 18) expresses that the entryways that open out to adjust are opened from within and now not from the outer.

Inspiration will likewise be inside (originating from inside oneself) (Lawrence and Jordan, 2009, p. 104), or outside (affected through various outside elements like human's comment on oneself et cetera) (Lawrence and Jordan, 2009, p. 104) and (Levoy, 2009, p. 18). Something the wellspring of inspiration is simply not as vital on the grounds that the productiveness (Foster et al., 2007, p. 1) that such inspiration is planned to have in the association (Ketkar and Sett, 2009, p. 1009). At that point, what moderately is inspiration (Rabey, 2009, p. 26), this that men and ladies continue aching for every day, and what hypothetical structures were put ahead with respect to inspirations? What techniques do outstanding organizations utilize to get their representatives energized? Does this influence the productiveness of the association (Foster et al., 2007, p. 1), (Johnson and Geupel, 2006) and (Shadare and Hammed, 2007).

Organizational efficiency at individual, collegial and institution phases are being jeopardized and subjected to more than a few organizational alterations. Notably, as developed organizations grew to be better, more multifaceted and more difficult, concerns about organizational performance abilities development and the way it might more likely to influence tradition and path of the institution have been in the forefronts of industry dialogues. There had been much to claim in regards to the function of motivation and their enlargement however very little has been performed on developing motivation-centered efficiency and far little motion on investigating organizational efficiency and its relative outcomes on worker's productiveness in companies.

That is the truth that all firms are counting on their men and women for the continuing survival and growth of their organization. Persons, or the staff, are the important thing in sustaining the group and this value of their role offers accountability to the organization to encourage them so that they can work more with ease. Motivation is the approach that account for an individual's depth, path and persistence of effort toward attainment of objectives. Motivation is the energizer of conduct and mother of all actions. Thus, motivation is straight associated with productivity. Productiveness refers back to the working effectiveness by which the staffs do their job and judged in line with their effectiveness and importance. We will additionally say that motivation is the willingness to work at a specific stage of effort. Motivation emerges, in present theories, out of desires, values, pursuits, intentions, and expectation. For the reason that motivation comes from within, managers ought to domesticate and direct the inducement that their staff have

already got.

A. Background of the Study

Now days doing trade far and wide the world is very challenging. Corporate efficiency and revenue growth are venture with the aid of inner and external operating environment causes to outlive in beneficial way in the enormously difficult and aggressive global market economy, all of the aspect of creation - laptop ,materials & men,- will have to be managed in a spectacular means among the causes of construction the human useful resource constitutes the most important assignment for the reason that unlike other inputs worker administration calls for entire dealing with of ideas, feelings & feelings to protected highest productivity. Excessive productiveness is a protracted-time period advantage of worker motivation. In this day and age, there are fast alterations in institution which elevated the markets and possibilities in phrases of gaining the development and revenues. Mostly, the inspiration of organizational change extra regards to the organizational vast trade that would comprise the change in time period of mission, restructuring operations, mergers, collaboration and others. There are study sayings that organizational trade approach group transformation (Kotter and Schlesinger 2008).

Consistent with Ashford et al., (2010), he says that the staff will start to have the feeling of nervousness, stress and absence of self-assurance when there are organizational alterations such as downsizing, restructuring as well as merging as noted in (Nicolaidis and Katsaros, 2009). The banking situation in Bangladesh has modified tremendously due to the fact that the Asian financial situation. After 53 years of independence from Pakistan, Bangladesh faced a variety of globalization comparable to staff in banking enterprise faces institution changes like reorganization as good as greater variant in workload because of fast technological alterations. The workers of the financial institution sectors could have the fear in the direction of the alterations of working environment, organizational culture and organization management. It is rather essential that workers ought to be physically attached to their banks. It may influence the effectivity and effectiveness of the institution and ultimately have an impact on the accomplishment of predetermined organizational targets as well as the employee's performance.

Regardless of all these obvious attendant problems of motivation, and productiveness, every organization do always seek means of making sure steady productiveness, which might be geared closer to the accomplishment of organization pursuits. The organizational method under study can't be stated to be unique in anyway, in phrases of producing the results for which it was installed. In all these procedures the exclusive company and indeed the banking industry has thus helped to make Bangladesh the nation it's today. Nonetheless these motives can certainly produce effect; the effect will mostly be much more short time period and can mean that staffs are forces on achieving business pursuits but rather on conveniently retaining their jobs.

B. Problem Statement

Organization exists for the motive of rendering some offerings. For the organization to fulfill its pursuits, humans are employed within the organization with the intention to aid the organization meet its pursuits. Accordingly, with a purpose to make sure that persons employed within the group participate in optimally toward the attention of organizational ambitions, they must be influenced to work. Motivating humans to work entails meeting their wants. There is a nice controversy over the challenge of motivating humans. Some persons are of the view that such extrinsic reasons like cash, reward, and high-quality of supervision and corporation's coverage can encourage persons to work, whilst others are of the view that such extrinsic causes like development great of the job performed by means of man or woman, consciousness and growth can motivate staff to productiveness. The communication network will become central when the environment is significantly converted. If there is a good communication between the employees and employers, and the appropriate understanding of strategic relevance of imposed organizational change being instructed, this will help the employee to take delivery of the exchange. Higher acceptance of the trade will lead employees to have higher performance. The worker's motivation may be very essential for helping the banking enterprise to acquire an excellent outcome, reputability and profitability. As a result, by giving an excellent benefit and reward to the workers will make them work hard to entire their undertaking successfully and readily.

2. Literature Review

In this research, there is influence of institution alterations in the direction of staff 'efficiency in banking enterprise. There is extraordinary opinion and assertion from extraordinary resources. Headquartered on the amassed information, there are five motives that being studied which are communication, management, procedural justice, workers 'development and tolerance to vary. These explanations are believed shall be priceless and valuable for the research.

A. Banking Industry in Bangladesh

The banking enterprise in Bangladesh has converted rapidly from transactional and customer service-orientated to increasingly aggressive surroundings wherein competition for returns is major concern. Due to this transformation, the employment culture in banking enterprise is changed and affected the personnel 'overall performance within the businesses. Banking enterprise is a vital industry for any international locations and it executes some of roles within the financial system. Financial institution the central Bank of Bangladesh is the vital bank of Bangladesh, which is answerable for coping with the economic coverage in Bangladesh. The bank is chargeable for ensuring the steadiness of financial gadget and selling advance monetary area. Besides, it develops the monetary device infrastructure and fosters the monetary inclusion in Bangladesh. The bank performs a vast banker and adviser role to the government as well (Bangladesh Bank, 2022).

Moreover, there are numbers of business banks in Bangladesh. According to Ghuslan, Muhammad and Abidin (2010), they determined that there had been 61 scheduled Banks runs in Bangladesh and 9 foreign bank operating beside local commercial bank in Bangladesh. Actually, there have been 43 private commercial banks functioning all over Bangladesh and rest of banks owned by the government. Moreover, the 9 foreign banks offer liaison services and clean the progress of facts change however now not perform the ordinary banking enterprise in Bangladesh. According to Ghuslan *et al.* (2010) the important uses of industrial banks are to provide the retail financial institution carrier, commerce monetary infrastructures, treasury services, and international payment service and custody offerings.

Because of the Asian financial disaster in year 2013 and 2020- 2023, it delivered a terrible effect to the banking enterprise within the countries of association of South-East kingdom (ASEAN). After the disaster, the officials of the unique countries restructured for the sake of reinforcing the banking enterprise. Consequently, there were worried the enhancement in control, acquisition and mergers of banks. Besides, after this disaster occurred in 2008, the characteristics of credit of every bank have been sizable dissimilarity (Okuda and Hashimoto, 2004).

There are several banks involved merging, for instant public bank merged with private bank proposed by the central bank of Bangladesh such as AB bank, Bangladesh commerce Bank, Padma bank, BASIC bank, National bank of Pakistan, Janata Bank, Agrani Bank and Rupali Bank. Zuniga-Vicente, Fuente-Sabate, and Suarez-Gonzalez (2005) observed that, banks will commonly merge with different banks to elevate their local office and provide contemporary financial services and products to increase their marketplace. The banks that concerned in merging and acquisition can reap a huge of capitals and belongings. Hence, the banks will become extra efficient, productivity and aggressive.

The turnover price of banking enterprise is founded very excessive in Bangladesh (Chan *et al.*, 2014). Employee's turnover is taken into consideration as a pricey dysfunction that each healthful enterprise should endeavor to decrease or cast off. As a result, the excessive or low turnover quotes of personnel 'will affect the companies 'overall performance (Hossain, M. A., Hossen, M. S., Ahad, A., & Wasantha, H. N.2024). Coping with this wonderful phenomenon, cross-field research studies on human capital and banking enterprise are keen valuable and attempt-worth to offer sensible tenet and strategic action for the ones banking organization to sustain employees (Hossain, M. A.2023).

B. Employees' Performance in Banking Industry

In this day and age, banking industry has developed in a timely fashion on the grounds that of growing on fiscal efficiency. The character of the banking enterprise is extraordinary from other industrial firms; the persons are more built-in within the subject of services. For this reason, first-rate workers ought to predict the success of the group at some point.

In keeping with Sparrow and Hilltop (2015) the earlier

studies acknowledged that the main key to have the capabilities to high within the organization performances is the recruitment and choice follow in the group, so the most important purpose of recruitment is to rent the right individuals to fill-up in the correct job function via a structured recruitment approach by means of choosing what characters that the employees ought to perform and gain the pursuits and ambitions of the institution. This may also be completed through the ways that use to decide on and recruit staff by means of a correct and potent evaluation, to choose the precise capabilities from the employees that being employed (Herzberg and Snyderman, 2024).

Most of the corporations are relying on the roles which might be performed by each individual. Employees who have just right accountability, talent and potential will accomplish the duties to fulfill and gain the institution's objectives and targets in an powerful ways. Hence, the businesses to success will impact by the employee's efficiency. A potent management is having satisfactory evidence on a robust worker engagement (Roberts, 2011). A further solution to support the performance of staff, is the organization are stimulated to give the employees benefit and rewards as to encourage them to achieve tasks or intention, and make them feel recognize and think that they're a part from the organization (Herzberg and Snyder man, 2015). There's a strong linkage between excessive-efficiency work techniques and company performance. Consequently, the employee efficiency can be bolstered by means of employee development software. According to Heskett (2013), The correct strategy that utilized in managing the humans can be made and measured situated on their performances (SAP, 2009). By using monitoring and evaluated the performance of the staff, it'll make them work tough and it does now not only will aid them comfortably to get promote after they get the excessive evaluation, it also will deliver the institution to success comfortably.

Consistent with Huselid (2007) the great recruitment and choice, job design, training and participation programs will broaden the proportion of staff involved in high efficiency work practices. A good worker may have the ability to solve the problems and meet with the challenges that they faced, and it'll always expand their efficiency and give a better carrier for patrons and making revenue for the companies (Heskett, 2008).

C. Organizational Changes

There are a lot of varieties of organizational alterations which comprise one-of-a-kind approaches comparable to downsizing, merger and acquisition and others. For example, the impact of group downsizing by lay-offing the staff in an organization will outcome in dissatisfaction among employees. The nature of the organization will have an impact on the theory of organizational change. Alternate approach —narrative describing a series of events of how development and alter unfold (Ven and Poole, 2009) as stated in (Kassim et al., 2010). Organizational exchange is mainly seen as an indispensable method to ensure that organizational methods continue to be achievable (Maya, 2009). On-going organizational alterations are more and more common within the office and include possibilities for development and progress as well because the potential for

titanic fees and losses (Kiefer, 2008) as referred to in (Ye et al., 2010). In step with Isabella (2009) as stated in (Ye et al., 2207) exchange can be outlined as trigger occasion a good way to stimulate an analysis system of perceptions, opinions, feelings and attitudes. Implementation of the changes tends to focus extra on the constructive alterations in work content that's outcomes via the intervention (Davis, 2005; Hackman and Oldham, 2006) as noted in (Roger and James, 2000).

At the same time, the downsizing could create monetary issues for workers who live on within the layoffs (Guiniven, 2008) as mentioned in (Malik, Ahmad and Hussain, 2010). That is considering the fact that the leftover staff after downsizing which might be often called layoff survivors (Virick et al., 2007) as cited in (Malik et al., 2010) confront complex circumstances including the work overload that explanations exhaustion that eventually leads to dissatisfaction. Exchange is primary to modern industry group considering the fact that it helps to maintain with evolving market demands and to remain competitive (Day, 1994) as referred to in (Ye, Marinova, & Singh, 2010). Implementing strategic alternate is a double-edged sword as it simultaneously generates expected performance attain and unexpected efficiency loss (Brown 2005; Kennedy, Goolsby, and Arnould 2003; Simesteret al.2011) as stated in (Ye et al., 2012). In addition, institution alterations will toughen the worker's work attitude such in job pleasure and productivity, (Miles, Hornstein, Callahan, Calder and Schiavo, 2013; Mann, 2013; Brown, 2009; Bowers, 2008; Hand, Estafen and Sims, 2008; Adams, 2009) as noted in (Edward and Lawrence, n.d.).

D. Employees' Performance

Employee efficiency in the institution is very predominant to determine manufacturer's success and profitability. In keeping with Chien (2007) found that a successful group require staff who're willing to do more than their ordinary job scope and make contributions performance that is beyond purpose's expectations. These days, lots of the firms will dealing with present day challenges and require put more attention on improving employees' performance (Bunhner, 2007) as stated in (Gruman & Saks, 2010). As a consequence, manufacturer ought to obstacle on recent developments in the organizational in order can create employees' capabilities to facilitate within the desired developed economies. In addition, organizational policies and daily practices must interact well to builds prior standard in workers' efficiency (Gruman & Saks, 2010). Some authors propose that victorious service firms equivalent to banking will invest assets or retaining the long term relationships in the programs as a way to expand job pleasure and workers' performance (Kusluvan, 2006) as mentioned in (Karatepe, Uludag, Menevis, Hadzimehmedagic and Baddar, 2006).

Moreover, according to Aryee, Chen & Pawan (2004) states that at the same time employee acquired rewards are perceived to be particularly allotted. Employees will probably be more inclined to contribute their inputs (efficiency) given that perceived they'll receive relatively allocation of output (rewards). These allocation tactics are perceptions of

organizational justice, procedural justice can positively related to organizational effects similar to organizational commitment, job satisfaction and project performance. Consequently, these all explanations will broaden staff 'efficiency more effectively (Cohen-Charash and Spector, 2006; Dirks and Ferrin, 2002) as referred to in (Hon and Lu, 2010). Additionally, some authors advise that, used of worker progress can enhance self-monitoring and lead to strengthen of employees' efficiency at the same time driven by means of the problems of downsizing, merger and re-institution routine (Blau, 2006; Cascio, 2002; Chadwick, Hunter, & Walston, 2004). Furthermore, staff 'progress practices incorporated teaching, service-associated coaching and empowerment can exceptional increase worker and organizational performance (Mathieu, 2000) as noted in (Blau *et al.*, 2008).

E. Communication

Communication is outlined as transmission or alternate of know-how, competencies, or ideas (Osif, 2010). Verbal exchange will also be by means of speech, writing or electronic media. The communication talent is often called capabilities that empower one to be in contact simply with other men and women. It's capacity for conveying understanding and suggestions with excellent listening and comprehension competencies (Osif, 2010). In step with Reinsch (2009) *communiqués* is outlined as a consciously intentional, verbal trade between individual human beings used by means of generally held symbols and reaching partial success. *Communiqués* is an important topic in any aspect of corporate life (Flock, 2006). Besides, Redding (n.d.) says that verbal exchange is behaviors of human beings or artifacts created by means of human beings which influence in messages (meaning) that being got by means of a number of folks as referred to in (Flock, 2006). In line with Johlke *et al.* (2000) as mentioned in Carter and grey (2007) *communiqués* is the key for the folks within and between businesses transfer and disseminate expertise. Interior verbal exchange will probably be primary to the alignment of the employee's perspective with the organizational goal (Gronroos, 2000) as referred to in (Carter *et al.*, 2007). Besides, it is suggests that two means conversation between the managers and the workers will result within the worker's efficiency and outcomes (Johlke and Duuhan, 2009) as stated in (Carter *et al.*, 2013).

Communication takes many varieties which involves verbal exchange local weather, supervisor *communiqués*, media best, horizontal conversation, organizational integration, individual suggestions, organizational point of view, high management verbal exchange, as well as subordinate verbal exchange. It is related to the communication delight inside the office and finally to job performance (Wanguri, 2014). When there is organizational trade, robust conversation is required. The staff who are very profession minded will put further vigor into the alternate verbal exchange which offers with the overall organizational trade and making extra commitment to support organizational trade effort (Arthur and Rousseau, 2001) as cited in Rashid and Zhao (2010).

F. Leadership

Leadership styles are established on different initiatives that the leaders give to their Human useful resource, development and training. In keeping with Howell and Frost (2000) show that a character will also be educate to display quite a lot of leadership behaviors, and the management patterns will also be determine, separate, and distinguish from every other. Various management theories together with claims signifying, strong leaders inspire (Locke, 2005). According to Stodgily (1974) states that management is a leader's behaviour into guiding a of individuals for the motive of intention achievement. Leadership has a major have an impact on the staff, managers, and companies performance. Leadership style plays a principal function in motivating subordinates to achieve the larger pursuits (Wang *et al.*, 2005). According to Denison, Hooijerg & Quinn (1995); Hart & Quinn (1993) as mentioned in (Wang *et al.*, 2011) leaders who participate in a multiple leadership roles will revel in an excessive level of organizational effectiveness. In addition, the leadership can help to develop the institution at some point. Apart from, there can also be in phrases of the managerial patterns, advertising proposal and ethics, provider, knowledge of the individuals and technical administration (Wahab *et al.*, 2009).

The certain challenges that leader faced is incorporate how to elevate the salience of collective identification and price in follower's self-standards by using linking the organizational mission to institution members and client's identification and worth. Apart from, additionally they ought to link the member's job behaviors to their identity and price (Perry *et al.*, 2009).

Leader's behavior has vigor to have an effect on the employee's notion closer to the job. Leader must detect the essential information from workers by means of related to daily problems and reply swiftly to their questions. Leaders also can use the formal conferences to acquire exclusive knowledge regarding an person's work growth or to talk about the work problems facing by them or in a small team. This assembly can accumulate the final know-how and opinions that regarding the issues that the employees faced. This would be the approach advised to aid the workers to achieve their work (Niehoff and Moorman, 1993).

G. Employees Development

In keeping with Swanson (2001) as noted in Hassan (2007) means that employees 'progress is a procedure of constructing or let unfastened knowledge by way of organization progress, coaching and progress for the intention of improving their efficiency. The basis believe of the staff development is the businesses are the human-made models that rely upon human capability for the sake of constituting and accomplishing their objectives and that experts are advocated of character and crew, work process and organizational trustworthiness (Hassan, 2007). In an effort to make stronger the group's competitive advantages of their market, training promotes raised of organization investment of their worker abilities and talents.

In line with Waterman *et al.* (1994) as referred to in (Tzafirir, Harel, Baruch and Dolan, 2004) means that staff 'development is watching ahead to set up assurance, toughen employability

and believe in administration. With its constructive final result, this investment raises employability for the staff themselves. In line with Fewick and Cieri (2004) as cited in Hassan and Yaqub (2010) means that the employees progress in the world networks efficiency is intervened via the ability to strengthen and preserve up network hub and faith, and through providing right career effect to stimulate man or woman community individuals for excellence efficiency.

In line with Holzer (1990); Lynch (1992); Bartel (1994); Pindus and Isbell (1997); Bloom and LaFleur (1999) endorse that the previous researches decide that these employers who offer training will raises their employee's productiveness as cited in (Horn and Fichtner, 2003). Bloom and LaFleur's be trained (1999) as cited in (Horn & Fichtner, 2003) means that the companies that provide worker training will intent the development in merchandise and offerings, decrease of production wastage, higher employee retention and employee-management members of the family. In addition, the learning can strengthen workers 'capacity which can enhance their efficiency and group's satisfaction.

Nevertheless, there are additionally drawbacks for ineffective staff 'progress. In line with Cheng and Ho (n.D.) state that motivation can have an effect on the trainees 'performance and influence as cited in Tabassi and Bakar (2009). Motivation can effect on the willingness of staff to present the designated programs, to position their effort on the software and hire the new skill and abilities to their work. As a consequence, this is hard to advantage from the learning if overlook the predominant of training motivation (Tabassi et al., 2009).

Apart from, in keeping with Zuurmond's gain knowledge of (2005) as cited in (Kahindi, 2011) propose that the educational chances are offered to bank representatives and again-office workers are numerous chiefly in skill and responsibility. The staff that work in entrance-administrative center are proficient in their works; wider understand of one-of-a-kind form of duties, extra empowerment. These front-places of work staff do not administer movement's duties as back-place of work employees. The cell human resource administration training is adopted through banks, whereby the expatriates excursion the financial institution's branches to provide on-web site coaching. The educational in verbal exchange is integral to be in contact effectually with customers who do not recognize the workers 'tune-pattern (Kahindi, 2011). Furthermore, the banks had invested in pc-based coaching from the 12 months of 1990. Thus, many of the workers were moving from green-monitor approach to a windows environment (Kiser, 2002). Therefore, some employees 'development exercitation such as training, coaching and empowerment will have an effect on the worker and group performance (Ellinger et al., 2008).

H. Empirical Evidence on Employee Motivation

The fields of employee motivation and employee performance are solidly grounded within the researcher of Maslow, Taylor, and Herzberg, to name just a few. The concepts of motivation and performance are constructs inside the larger organizational conduct version. While each of those

constructs may be reviewed on their personal, employee motivation is linked carefully to worker performance. In 'past the perimeter', Simms discusses how diverse corporations make use of tailored versions of "non-coins rewards" as employee incentives. Simms shows that Herzberg's view of income as no longer being a motivator holds. The capacity to preserve up an incentive that doesn't get absorbed with the aid of the worker's month-to-month payments has a bigger effect on worker motivation. He additionally shows it can be extra ideal to boast about a special award or birthday party as opposed to a worker's profits boost. Simms then is going on to extend the discussion of non-coins rewards such as flex time, employee of the month, and tailored intention incentives. Simms argues it's far vital for employers to communicate those benefits to personnel because many employees don't recognize their total compensation package. Through communicating the overall package, the enterprise reinforces their commitment to the personnel and enables to encourage the worker. This motivation results in more employee satisfaction and performance (Simms, 2007).

The case have a look at of the Harrah's entertainment income groups lays out the use of group incentives to growth income across the diverse branches of the Harrah's enjoyment family of merchandise. However, the core to the motivation programs, that Jakobson discusses, is using merchandise Awards. Jakobson states that products Awards are even extra powerful than pinnacle seller trips. Harrah's also uses simple worker motivation techniques inclusive of reputation at weekly and month-to-month income meetings of the top income teams (Jakobson, 2007). Personnel need to experience their tales are being heard, understood, and valued via the ones asking for the memories. By using forging these relationships, the worker feels valued via the organization, manager, and organization as a contributor. This cost interprets into better work overall performance and stake inside the agency (Silverman, 2006; Whiting, 2007).

A common thread of verbal exchange among employers and personnel emerges as a requirement for worker motivation (Simms, 2007; Jakobson, 2007; Whiting, 2007; Silverman, 2006; & Sharbrough, 2006). Many of those case studies hyperlink high worker motivation with improved employee performance (Simms, 2007; Jakobson, 2007; Whiting, 2007; Silverman, 2006; & Sharbrough, 2006). By first utilising Kellerman's "level of engagement" category, a business enterprise can tailor the usage of ML and motivational strategies inside the business enterprise. In this manner, worker motivation may be maximized to growth worker performance via focusing the usage of ML and motivational strategies.

I. Theories of Motivation

1) Abraham Maslow Theories

Abraham Maslow (1954) endeavored to integrate an expansive assortment of research identified with human inspiration, before Maslow, analysts by and large centered on such components as science, accomplishment, or energy to clarify what empowers, coordinates, and supports human conduct. Maslow set a pecking order of human needs in light of

two groupings: insufficiency needs and development needs. Inside the inadequacy needs, each lower require must be met before moving to the following more elevated amount. Once each of these necessities has been fulfilled, if at some future time an inadequacy is distinguished, the individual will act to evacuate the insufficiency. Maslow's needs chain of importance hypothesis is a standout amongst the most prominent speculations of work inspiration in our time however it was not generally so.

2) *Frederick Winslow Taylor Theory of Motivation*

Frederick Winslow Taylor (1856 – 1917) set forward the possibility that specialists are propelled mostly by pay. His Theory of Scientific Management contended the accompanying:

Laborers don't normally appreciate work thus require close supervision and control Therefore chiefs ought to separate generation into a progression of little undertakings.

Specialists ought to then be given suitable preparing and devices so they can fill in as proficiently as conceivable on one set undertaking. Laborers are then paid by the quantity of things they deliver in a set timeframe piece-rate pay. Subsequently specialists are urged to buckle down and expand their efficiency.

Taylor's techniques were broadly embraced as organizations saw the advantages of expanded profitability levels and lower unit costs. The most strikingly promoter was Henry Ford who utilized them to outline the principal ever generation line, making Ford autos. This was the begin of the time of large scale manufacturing. Taylor's approach has close connections with the idea of an imperious administration style (administrators take every one of the choices and essentially offer requests to those underneath them) and Macgregor's Theory X way to deal with specialists (laborers are seen as apathetic and wish to stay away from duty). However, laborers soon came to abhorrence Taylor's approach as they were just given exhausting, dreary assignments to do and were being dealt with minimal superior to anything human machines

3) *Frederick Herzberg Theory of Motivation*

Frederick Herzberg (1923) had close connections with Maslow and put stock in a two-calculate hypothesis of inspiration. He contended that there were sure variables that a business could present that would straightforwardly propel representatives to work harder (Motivators). However, there were likewise calculates that would de-spur a worker if not present but rather would not in themselves really rouse representatives to work harder (Hygienefactors).

Herzberg trusted that organizations ought to spur representatives by embracing a popularity-based way to deal with administration and by enhancing the nature and substance of the real occupation through specific strategies. A portion of the strategies directors could use to accomplish this are:

Work expansion – laborers being given a more noteworthy assortment of assignments to perform (not really all the more difficult) which ought to make the work all the more fascinating.

Work improvement – includes laborers being given a more extensive scope of more perplexing, intriguing and testing

assignments encompassing a total unit of work. This ought to give a more noteworthy feeling of accomplishment. Strengthening implies assigning more energy to representatives to settle on their own choices over territories of their working life.

J. Incentives as Motivational Tools

To keep laborers propelled their requirements must be tended to as venture objectives are come to. Fulfilling laborers' needs can be seen as dispersing motivating forces when certain destinations are accomplished. Laborers who are propelled to help achieve the objective of the business and as such ought to be perceived with a motivating force/remunerate. There are a wide range of sorts of motivator arrangements, with the yearly execution reward plan being the best known. Benefit sharing arrangements are additionally exceptionally normal, and the vast majority in the workforce has ideally experienced no less than one of these methodologies. Each extraordinary kind of motivating force arranges has both advantages and disadvantages. A yearly execution reward is extremely rare, once yearly, and along these lines hard to interface together with execution. This kind of motivating force arrange additionally tends to bring about to representatives to concentrate on what makes them look great, some of the time to the detriment of what might be best for the organization's primary concern (Turkson, 2002).

K. Types of Motivation

1) Extrinsic Motivation

It is identified with substantial rewards, for example, compensation and incidental advantages, security, advancement, contract of administration, the workplace and states of administration. These are what should be done to or for individuals to inspire them. They are frequently decided at the authoritative level and might be to a great extent outside the control of the individual chiefs. Extraneous inspirations can have a prompt and intense impact yet won't fundamental keep going long (Mullins, 2005; Armstrong, 2006). Katz, in Sinclair, (2005) shows the motivational influence of cash through the procedure of employment decision. He clarifies that cash has the ability to draw in, hold, and rouse people towards higher execution. Bernard and Stoner (2005), proposes the accompanying are impetuses for representatives: Salary, Wages and Conditions of Service: To utilize compensations as an inspiration viably, work force supervisors must consider four noteworthy segments of a pay structures.

2) Intrinsic Motivation

This is identified with mental rewards, for example, the chance to utilize one's capacity. A feeling of test and accomplishment, accepting thankfulness, positive acknowledgment, and being dealt with in a minding and kind way. Mental prizes are those that can generally be dictated by the activities and conduct of the individual administrators (Mullins, 2005). Natural helpers are worried with the nature of work life, are probably going to have a more profound and longer-term impact since they are inborn in people and not forced from outside (Armstrong, 2006).

3) Non-material Incentives

Additionally at the nearby level, non-materialistic social and inherent inspiration can assume a noteworthy part that should be investigated. It is justifiable that many individuals might be hesitant to be posted far from home. Those used to urban life will discover it especially hard to move to a remote region. In Thailand the test has been pivoted into an advantage by enrolling learners from the very zones they should serve in. This approach was discovered fruitful (Hongoro 2002).

L. The Psychology of Tangible Non-Monetary Incentives

Financial favorable circumstances, for example, these can be huge yet they don't catch the greater part of the potential advantages made by the utilization of unmistakable non-fiscal motivations. This segment will talk about reasons why representatives may apply more exertion in quest for a substantial non-fiscal honor than a money reward equivalent to the cost of that impetus, regardless of the possibility that workers express an inclination for the money. There are various mental systems that would bring about a non-fiscal impetus to outflank money as a propelling apparatus on a dollar-for-dollar premise. A non-money related prize may expand the anticipated utility of the honor, the utility related with acquiring the honor, or increment the measure of exertion the representative gives on a for each unit esteem premise.

M. Effects of Motivation on Productivity

Profitability when all is said in done has been characterized in the Cambridge International and Oxford Advance Learner's word references as the rate at which merchandise are delivered with reference to number of individuals and measure of materials important to create it. Then again, profitability has been characterized as the use of assets in delivering an item or administrations (Gaissey, 1993). It has further been characterized as the proportion of the yield (great and administrations) and info (Labor, capital or administration). The meaning of efficiency is used by financial analysts at the modern level to decide the economy's wellbeing, patterns and development rate whiles at the venture level, it applies to regions of arranging, cost evaluating, bookkeeping and cost control (Mojahed, 2005).

N. Effects of Motivation on Performance

The execution of representatives will represent the deciding moment an organization; this is the reason it is vital to discover an assortment of strategies for spurring workers. "Inspiration is the readiness to accomplish something," composed Stephen Robbins and David A. DeCenzo in their book "Supervision Today." "It is molded by this present activity's capacity to fulfill some requirement for the person." The clearest type of inspiration for a worker is cash; in any case, there are other persuading components that must be considered.

3. Research Methodology

The data was collected from the employees of Janata Bank in Bangladesh. The sample size 474 staff was examined such as Management staff 25, Permanent staff 294 and Contract staff

155. The respondents were participated in the online Google survey to contribute this research. Two essential straightforward scientific instruments were utilized as a part of the investigation such as utilization of straightforward rate and the Chi-Square strategy for theory testing. Basically this research study was developed based on the research framework and purpose to investigate the impact of motivation on the employee productivity of Janata bank in Bangladesh.

A. Hypotheses Study

- 1) *H1*: There is positive relationship between incentives and work productivity for of Janata Bank.
- 2) *H2*: There is positive relationship between monetary incentives and rewards exert a higher effect on employees than some other Styles of motivational incentives.
- 3) *H3*: There is positive relationship between the first-class of supervision inspire employee's and productivity
- 4) *H4*: There is positive relationship in a worker's perception of what received in his organizational will not motivate him to larger productiveness.
- 5) *H5*: An employee's belief of organizational appraisal coverage will inspire him to larger productivity
- 6) *H6*: The employee's pleasure with its fringe advantages is not going to encourage him to higher productivity.

B. Respondent Population (Staff Age)

This section dissects the individual information got from the respondents that constitute the specimen of the review. The number of inhabitants in the review was seven hundred and fourteen (714) staff of Janata Bank. The specimen size was comprised of five hundred and eighty (580) sadly four hundred and seventy-four (474) reacted as appeared in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

Source: Field Survey 2024

C. Discussion of the Results

This review was expected to explore regardless of whether there was a relationship between satisfactory inspiration components and laborers efficiency in an association. The factors used to order the respondents were involvement and age. The information created in this review was broke down and the discoveries are talked about under this making a beeline for the different research addresses that were detailed to control the review.

The finding from this review as it identifies with research address one, demonstrated that there are motivators and

motivational calculates connection to laborers profitability and execution. The finding of this review authenticates the discoveries contained in the review directed by Dachler and Hullin in which 400 auto assembly line laborers were utilized as a part of Chicago. The real finding of that review was that 57% of the respondent's regardless of the current pay rise they got demonstrated that none of motivational components has any ramifications on their work efficiency. It was seen in this review regardless of the way that none of the motivational elements has influenced the laborer; administration concern had a higher coefficient.

The finding of this exploration address as it identifies with Janata Bank concurs with the discoveries of the reviews completed by George and Bishop. The analysts prevailing with regards to giving proof such that a positive relationship exists between the measure of motivations and level profitability in a life coverage organization. Twelve work areas with high profitability and twelve with low efficiency were chosen for the review. The conduct of impetuses in these two arrangements of work segments were evaluated by method for meetings with both bosses and subordinates. The outcome demonstrated a calculable contrast in the measure of thought that sufficient impetuses and high profitability administration gave their specialists. In another review by Freeman in which 242 electronic laborers were utilized, it was watched that 73% of the considerable number of respondents demonstrated that recognition was the motivating forces that most influenced their work efficiency. By chance, the finding does not concur with the finding of this review, which demonstrated that closeness had the most reduced coefficient of -0.525 . The workplace and might be the way of business and society may have been in charge of the absence of consistency in the acquired outcomes.

Q1. An incentive is important for motivation of workers

Fig. 2.

The finding from this review as it identifies with research address one, demonstrated that there are impetuses and motivational figures connection to laborers profitability and execution. The finding of this review verifies the discoveries contained in the review led by Dachler and Hullin in which 400 auto assembly line laborers were utilized as a part of Chicago. The real finding of that review was that 57% of the respondent's regardless of the current pay rise they got demonstrated that none of motivational variables has any ramifications on their work profitability. It was seen in this review disregarding the way that none of the motivational elements has influenced the specialist; administration concern had a higher coefficient.

The finding of this examination address as it identifies with Janata Bank concurs with the discoveries of the reviews completed by George and Bishop. The scientists prevailing with regards to giving confirmation such that a positive relationship exists between the measure of motivations and level efficiency in a life coverage organization. Twelve work areas with high profitability and twelve with low efficiency were chosen for the review. The conduct of impetuses in these two arrangements of work areas were surveyed by method for meetings with both directors and subordinates. The outcome demonstrated an obvious contrast in the measure of thought that satisfactory impetuses and high profitability administration gave their specialists. In another review by Freeman in which 242 electronic specialists were utilized, it was watched that 73% of the considerable number of respondents demonstrated that nature was the motivators that most influenced their work efficiency. Unexpectedly, the finding does not concur with the finding of this review, which demonstrated that closeness had the least coefficient of -0.525 . The workplace and might be the way of business and society may have been in charge of the absence of consistency in the got comes about.

Q2. It is important that the Chief Executive Officer motivate staff

Table 1

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	20	20
Agree	31	31
Undecided	26	26
Disagree	14	14
Strongly Disagree	9	9
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

A view, which underpins the finding from this review, is that from Evan who contended that motivational elements, for example, administration/worker relations and interpersonal relations tend to influence both ways to deal with work and profitability. In another review by Freeman, it was found that there was a diminishment in efficiency on the grounds that there was some level of incongruence between the formal casual associations. This demonstrated there was a noteworthy relationship between motivational components, for example, worries to work, as is additionally the case in the review. What the finding in Freeman's work uncovers, is that the different motivational variable could influence profitability either emphatically or contrarily.

It is the constructive outcomes of the different motivational components on specialist that the association is probably endeavoring to take a shot at by getting the apparatus under way by looking into states of administration on two-year premise including the retirement time of staff. The significance of the impact of satisfactory inspiration calculates on specialist can't be over-stressed whether the issue is taking a gander at it from the mental, sociological and monetary perspective.

Larger part of the respondents held that view that closeness was a figure the development of particular way to deal with work. Unexpectedly, a large portion of the respondents were youthful and new participants into the work advertise.

Q3. Workers put in their best when they are placed on little or no incentive package

Fig. 3. Frequency

Source: Field Survey 2024

The outcome got from old individuals from staff, demonstrated that there was no critical relationship between the motivational components and way to deal with work. A further breakdown of the outcome demonstrates that while closeness and concern did not record critical associations with way to deal with work, main thrust recorded noteworthy relationship. This outcome may have been affected by the age of the respondents who may have felt more worried about issues that touch on sense of pride more than whatever other variable.

Q4. It seems that fat salaries are the best tools with which to motivate workers increase productivity

Table 2

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	6	6
Agree	28	28
Undecided	8	8
Disagree	22	22
Strongly Disagree	36	36
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

The American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language (2006) characterized worker "as a man who works for another as a byproduct of money related or other remuneration". Representatives don't work since they need to gather just pay however for different various variables. Individuals work since they have objectives to accomplish which outperform monetary profits from their business. There are different elements that trouble on work. These components include: business, worker, working condition, working terms and conditions and kind of items and administrations gave by boss.

Maslow (1943) said that individuals work to survive and survive money related pay, to make new companions, to have employer stability, for a feeling of accomplishment and to feel critical in the general public, to have a feeling of character, and most particularly to have work fulfillment. All representatives that have work fulfillment are superior workers in their separate work environments.

Q5. Well-motivated staff has a positive attitude towards work

It is said that impetuses assume a noteworthy part in spurring your representatives and urging them to accomplish higher objectives. In any association, motivations work since representatives are then objective driven and drive themselves

to accomplish their objectives. Every association has a reward framework set up to inspire their representatives. This reward framework depends on motivating forces like an expansion in the pay, money, blessing or an occasion. Pay is offered to every worker in light of his or her execution at work. Impetuses are typically observed as here and now inspirations for representatives. Consequently, impetuses are utilized a considerable measure to rouse deals workers with the goal that they accomplish their objectives.

Fig. 4.

Source: Field Survey 2015

Q6. Workers' welfare should be a paramount issue of concern to top management who wish to have higher productivity

Table 3

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	3	3
Agree	79	79
Undecided	0	0
Disagree	5	5
Strongly Disagree	13	13
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

In these difficult circumstances, your staff confidence is of vital significance. They're stressed over their occupations and making a decent living, having low spirit at work will aggravate their misfortunes. In all actuality as you try to lift staff confidence, you'll be expanding efficiency, bringing down representative truancy and in addition consistent worker turnover.

Investigating Janata Bank Bangladesh, it was understood that medicinal, garments, furniture, fuel stipends and additionally exceptional festivals for Christmas/Easter/Salah and end of year gatherings sorted out for staff, for the most part administration, senior and additionally junior staff. That is why we have greater part of the staff consenting to this announcement that staff welfare ought to be of central issue to top administration.

Q7. Workers will still perform well even if their salary is delayed

Most staffs rely on upon their pay rates so they and their families will survive. Practically every staff anticipates 'pay day' so they can bring home something for the family. At the point when pay rates are postponed, it influences the staff worried as well as his/her family also who in various routes add

to him/her having a sound personality to work for higher efficiency.

Fig. 5.

Source: Field Survey 2024

The outcomes from this review demonstrated the greater part of the populace contradicting this. Only somewhat concurred and the individuals who concurred are the administration staff that aside their pay rates, have different impetuses that can compensate for the pay rates regardless of the possibility that deferred. Compensations postponed will bring about staff failing to meet expectations because of a considerable measure of reasons including weight from home from dependents that were planning to get something from the staff worried toward the finish of the month. Compensations postponed hoses staffs spirits and they don't have the inclination or peace to work adequately.

Q8. Inter-Personal relationship between top management and staff should be encouraged

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	33	33
Agree	29	29
Undecided	3	3
Disagree	14	14
Strongly Disagree	21	21
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

Opening the entryways for powerful interpersonal correspondence between chiefs, representatives, and colleagues will expand profitability and fulfillment on all levels. Individuals are exceptional and must be overseen, instructed and bolstered in a way that gains by their uniqueness.

Powerful correspondence originates from the correct blend of manner of speaking, words, non-verbal communication and pace of discourse and activities. These four ranges are the segments of a man's behavioral style. We have to adjust our conduct keeping in mind the end goal to discuss viably with others.

Q9. Recreational facilities are important in every organization

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	19	19
Agree	38	38
Undecided	21	21
Disagree	22	22
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

Individuals get a kick out of the chance to work in a domain that is agreeable; they can get wore out if the workplace is absolutely genuine and entirely business. Awesome organizations like Southwest Airlines have thought of innovative routes for representatives to have a ton of fun. I think each supervisor ought to peruse the hit book, NUTS! By Southwest administrator, Herb Kelleher. In case you're not actually great at inspiring individuals to have a ton of fun, assign a key worker to accept this part. Hugh Gold Thorpe, who is a top official with Owens and Minor of Richmond, Virginia, has received (and had imprinted on his business cards) his official occupation title as: Head Cheerleader.

Q10. Favoritism on the part of the MD/CEO can contribute too much productivity

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	11	11
Agree	12	12
Undecided	18	18
Disagree	35	35
Strongly Disagree	24	24
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

Representatives may be proficient, qualified and experienced, yet they're still human and still defenseless to feelings better left outside the work environment. Envy, outrage, dread, dourness and stress can happen in business condition whenever, however these negative feelings are exacerbated when bias happens. Before enjoying working environment bias, consider how your activities may influence different specialists.

Preference in the work environment implies giving special treatment to at least one representative. Particular treatment can be purposeful; for instance, a business could allot the choicest obligations to the most veteran specialist or superstar upstart by clarifying that his capacities legitimize the additional consideration and assignments. Particular treatment can likewise be subliminal; for instance, representatives may see that a more seasoned male director appears to treat youthful female laborers with benevolent grins and support while amiably overlooking male specialists in the lobbies.

On the off chance that representatives feel that they're being ignored for new obligations or advancements since all treats are channeled toward most loved laborers, bring down inspiration comes about. Representative's slack off, bringing less care with appointed obligations and being more hesitant to volunteer for extra assignments. This outcomes in lower efficiency, missed due dates and lower general spirit.

Q11. Staff work best when working equipment and facilities are adequately provided. (Frequency)

Managers have obligations regarding the wellbeing and security of their representatives. They are additionally in charge of any guests to their premises, for example, clients, providers and the overall population. Your manager has an 'obligation of care' to take care of, beyond what many would consider

possible, your wellbeing, security and welfare while you are grinding away. They ought to begin with a hazard appraisal to spot conceivable wellbeing and security perils.

Fig. 6.

Source: Field Survey 2024

They need to name a 'skilled individual' with wellbeing and security duties. This is generally one of the proprietors in littler firms, or an individual from staff prepared in wellbeing and security in bigger organizations.

A bigger extent of those talked with consented to this reality as delineated in the table above.

Q12. Receiving credit for work done affects your morale at work

Table 7

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	71	71
Agree	8	8
Undecided	1	1
Disagree	3	3
Strongly Disagree	17	17
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

Everybody likes to be lauded. When we get kudos for work done, it helps our assurance to accomplish higher profitability. From the table above, it is clear that the staff of Janata Bank is not the same as the standard; they likewise jump at the chance to be applauded for work done. 71% of the staff talked with, which is very nearly seventy five percent of all met, were of the view that getting kudos for work done influences assurance at work and this in no less way help increment profitability.

Q13. Working attitude is affected by the challenges encountered on the job

Table 8

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	29	29
Agree	41	41
Undecided	8	8
Disagree	11	11
Strongly Disagree	11	11
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

At the point when the difficulties at work are various and they are ones that can't be dealt with effectively by staff, the staff state of mind to work is poor and this influences the assurance of the staff which thusly influences clients along these lines influencing efficiency and the other way around. The greater part of the aggregate populace talked with consented to this reality. The individuals, who deviated, upon meeting, were the

individuals who felt they generally need to set up a grinning face keeping in mind the end goal to secure their occupation.

Q14. Rewarding good work and excellence can contribute to more excellence and healthy competition

This is in reference to question 12. Remunerating great work and greatness can add to more fabulousness and solid rivalry. At the point when other staff see that their partners are being compensated for the great work they are doing, they will likewise endeavor to work harder to get such rewards. This opposition is no chance unfortunate. It for sure is sound and advances higher generation.

Fig. 7. Frequency

Source: Field Survey 2024

Q15. Only monetary rewards can bring out the best in workers

Table 9

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	5	5
Agree	7	7
Undecided	3	3
Disagree	38	38
Strongly Disagree	47	47
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

With reference to question 4, it is not just money related prizes that can draw out the best in specialists. There are different components or motivating forces that staff pay special mind to similarly as has been said in the investigation on question 4.

D. Test of Hypothesis

Various speculations were expressed in part one. Be that as it may, for straightforwardness just two of these speculations were tried. Motivating forces as has been talked about from part two are a to a great degree substantial subject in human asset administration.

The two hypotheses we shall be testing are:

1) *Hypothesis 1*

There is no significant relationship between incentives and work productivity for workers at Janata Bank.

2) *Hypothesis 2*

Monetary incentives and rewards exert a stronger influence on workers than any other form of motivational incentives. The Chi-Square (X²) analytical method was used to test the hypotheses as stated above.

$$X^2 = \sum (Of - Ef)^2$$

Ef

Where X² = Chi-Square

Of = Observed frequency

Ef = Expected frequency

Σ= Summation (Addicts on sign)

To demonstrate these theories, some significant inquiries from the survey were chosen taking after the relating information in section four.

To verify hypothesis 1: questions 5 and 8 on the questionnaire were used. Question 5 states thus: Well-motivated staffs have a positive attitude towards work.

Question 8 states thus: Inter-Personal link between top management and staff should be encouraged.

The data/figures reached/got by these questions were tabulated into a contingency table.

Table 10
Question 5 & 8 test of hypotheses contingency table

Options	Questions		Total
	5	8	
Strongly Agree	46 ₁	33 ₆	79
Agree	22 ₂	29 ₇	51
Undecided	13 ₃	3 ₈	16
Strongly Disagree	10 ₄	14 ₉	24
Disagree	9 ₅	21 ₁₀	30
Total	100	100	200

Source: Field Survey 2024

The next logical step is to calculate Ef (Expected frequencies) for the already Observed frequencies (Of) of the boxes labeled 1, 2.....10 in an italic format in the table.

$$E1 = \frac{79 \times 100}{200} = 39.5$$

$$E4 = \frac{24 \times 100}{200} = 12$$

$$E7 = \frac{51 \times 100}{200} = 25.5$$

$$E2 = \frac{51 \times 100}{200} = 25.5$$

$$E5 = \frac{30 \times 100}{200} = 15$$

$$E8 = \frac{16 \times 100}{200} = 8$$

$$E3 = \frac{16 \times 100}{200} = 8$$

$$E6 = \frac{79 \times 100}{200} = 39.5$$

$$E9 = \frac{24 \times 100}{200} = 12$$

$$E10 = \frac{30 \times 100}{200} = 15$$

Applying the formula $X^2 = \sum \frac{(Of - Ef)^2}{Ef}$

$$X^2 = \frac{(46 - 39.5)^2}{39.5} + \frac{(22 - 25.5)^2}{25.5} + \frac{(13 - 8)^2}{8} + \frac{(10 - 12)^2}{12} + \frac{(9 - 15)^2}{15} + \frac{(33 - 39.5)^2}{39.5}$$

$$+ \frac{(29 - 25.5)^2}{25.5} + \frac{(3 - 8)^2}{8} + \frac{(14 - 12)^2}{12} + \frac{(21 - 15)^2}{15}$$

$$X^2 = 1.07 + 0.48 + 3.13 + 0.33 + 2.40 + 1.07 + 0.48 + 3.13 + 0.33 + 2.40$$

$$X^2 = 14.82$$

The next step is to calculate df (degrees of freedom). $df = (r - 1)(c - 1)$ where r = number of rows and c = number of columns. Where our contingency table, r = 5 and c = 2. $df = (5 - 1)(2 - 1) = 4 \times 1 = 4$.

Assuming a 5% level of significance, when $df = 4$, the value of X^2 from the table of critical values = 9.49.

Decision:

Since the computed estimation of X^2 (14.82) surpasses or is more noteworthy than the basic estimation of X^2 (9.49), we dismiss the invalid speculation and acknowledge the option, which would express that there is a critical relationship between motivational variables and work efficiency for staff of Janata Bank.

This huge relationship is upheld by Vroom in his "work and inspiration" (1964) He trusted that there is extensive proof that execution or profitability builds given satisfactory reward. This under lying conviction is depended on his anticipation hypothesis as it is at some point called. As indicated by him individuals will be roused to do certain thing to accomplish specific objectives. In the event that they know or expect that specific activity on their part will help them accomplish certain objective. Besides this suspicion bolster that specialists will be spurred to play out a specific assignment not on account of its including and testing nature or because its capacity to concede firm acknowledgment, obligation and self-actualization as challenge by Herzberg (1959) Mergrofor (1960) and Mc Chellan (1961).

Hypothesis 2:

For the sake of verifying hypothesis 2, questions 4 and 10 were considered.

Question 4 states thus: *Fat salaries are the top tools with which to motivate employees.*

Question 15 states thus: *Only monetary rewards can bring out the greatest in labors.*

As it has been already stated, hypothesis two states thus: - *Monetary incentives and rewards exert a stronger effect on workers than any other form of motivational aspect.*

Tabulating the data/figures of these questions shall take us to the contingency table below:

Table 11
Question 4&15 test of hypotheses contingency table

Options	Questions		Total
	4	15	
Strongly Agree	6 ₁	5 ₆	11
Agree	28 ₂	7 ₇	35
Undecided	8 ₃	3 ₈	11
Strongly Disagree	22 ₄	38 ₉	60
Disagree	36 ₅	47 ₁₀	83
Total	100	100	200

Source: Field Survey 2024

Once again, let's calculate the Expected frequencies (Ef) of the boxes labeled 1, 2, 3...10.

$$E1 = \frac{11 \times 100}{200} = 5.5$$

$$E5 = \frac{83 \times 100}{200} = 41.5$$

$$E9 = \frac{60 \times 100}{200} = 30$$

$$200$$

$$200$$

$$200$$

$$E2 = \frac{35 \times 100}{200} = 17.5$$

$$E6 = \frac{11 \times 100}{200} = 5.5$$

$$E10 = \frac{83 \times 100}{200} = 41.5$$

$$200$$

$$200$$

$$200$$

$$E3 = \frac{11 \times 100}{200} = 5.5$$

$$E7 = \frac{35 \times 100}{200} = 17.5$$

$$200$$

$$200$$

$$E4 = \frac{60 \times 100}{200} = 30$$

$$E8 = \frac{11 \times 100}{200} = 5.5$$

$$200$$

$$200$$

$$\text{Applying the formula } X^2 = \frac{\sum(\text{Of} - \text{Ef})^2}{\text{Ef}}$$

Then, we'll calculate df. Also, $r = 5$ and $C = 2$ in contingency table 11... $df = (5-1)(2-1) = 4$.

Assuming a level of significance of 5% (0.05), when $df = 4$, the corresponding value of

X^2 on the critical table of X^2 values = 9.49.

$$\begin{aligned} X^2 &= \frac{(6 - 5.5)^2}{5.5} + \frac{(28 - 17.5)^2}{17.5} + \frac{(8 - 5.5)^2}{5.5} + \frac{(22 - 30)^2}{30} + \frac{(36 - 41.5)^2}{41.5} + \frac{(5 - 5.5)^2}{5.5} \\ &\quad + \frac{(7 - 17.5)^2}{17.5} + \frac{(3 - 5.5)^2}{5.5} + \frac{(38 - 30)^2}{30} + \frac{(47 - 41.5)^2}{41.5} \\ &= 0.05 + 6.3 + 1.14 + 2.13 + 0.73 + 0.05 + 6.3 + 1.14 + 2.13 + 0.73 \\ X^2 &= 20.7 \end{aligned}$$

Then, we'll calculate df. Also, $r = 5$ and $C = 2$ in contingency table 11... $df = (5-1)(2-1) = 4$.

Assuming a level of significance of 5% (0.05), when $df = 4$, the corresponding value of

X^2 on the critical table of X^2 values = 9.49.

Decision:

Since the computed estimation of X^2 (20.7) surpasses the basic estimation of X^2 (9.49), we dismiss the invalid theory and acknowledge the option. All things considered, we infer that money related motivators and prizes don't apply more grounded impact on specialists than whatever other type of motivational element.

By and by and the fundamental rule of reasonable administration justify pay has been fought that it doesn't spur, it could fortify superior, smother low execution, increment instrumentalities, wellbeing needs, accomplish value et cetera. The reason it doesn't work needs to do with execution and the way of practice that abuse the rule. Frequently execution measures are not substantial or precise. The financial backing is normally little without much adaptability. Directors are hesitant to give little raises that are annoying or lower than the average cost for basic items and they would prefer not to make foes or be blamed for favoring their companions.

4. Summary of Findings

The review however uncovered the way that motivations as main impetus did not convey as much weight as concern and main impetus as far as influencing the way to deal with work of the respondents. The review tried to demonstrate the impact of the above expressed factors on the conduct of the laborers in Janata Bank. In this manner, this review investigated the association and its execution regarding the expressed goals. Specifically, the review inspected the impacts of sufficient motivators and motivational figures other than cash the powerful working of the association and offers recommendations for development. Administration travel every which way, however the laborers remains and in truth remains

dependably the proceeding with connection and constrain.

This review was begun and completed on the start that cash (compensation) or budgetary motivator being a privilege of the specialist is underestimated and that specific different components would be expected to sufficiently rouse or fulfill the laborers. Such elements incorporate professional stability, acknowledgment and so forth the new component of unpredictable or nor installment of pay rates in the association which got to be distinctly present after the review was considered and begun, nonetheless, tended to somewhat adjust the discoveries of this review with a little tilt towards the significance of budgetary reward.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This review uncovered that the specialist's motivational procedures in Janata Bank have experienced enormous change since the association was set up. The appearing loss of a standout amongst the most valued and begrudged signs of the association employer stability and the vulnerabilities about wages and pay rates would seem to have enormously influenced the specialists confidence wherever in Bangladesh. Under such a condition, laborers can't put forth a strong effort and expected return or yield from the occupation. The administration would now need to make a pressing move to investigate the issue if the representative is to accomplish her expressed goals. Also, in light of the discoveries of this review, the accompanying proposals are offered for the future inspiration of representatives:

- In restraining officers, the beyond any doubt procedures ought to be taken after and the officers ought to be given a hearing and chance to protect any allegations of wrong doing.
- There ought to be more counsel between the board and the administrators on one hand, and the supervisors and the laborers on the other. The utilization of the interior notice as the channel of settling emergency or discussing grievances with the staff by the line administrators ought to be stopped.
- Staff advancement to upgrade profitability and advance self-satisfaction ought to be energized as an issue of think approach.
- There ought to be an audit of the announcing framework and detailing staff ought to be accepted in the demonstration of answering to make the reviewing in the reports more uniform.
- The CEO of Janata Bank ought to build up a sufficient motivational unit in the bank whose principle capacity will be to screen and advance assurance boosting exercises in the bank. Such a Unit ought to complete reviews on the welfare of the laborers contrast with comparable association, and make accessible their discoveries and information for arranging and execution of reward framework in the Janata Bank.
- There is have to angle out abilities for reward to fill in as motivating force to them, and make a goal for others to go for.

- The administration ought to endeavor at presenting staff transport; cafeteria fabricating in order to give better and reasonable unwinds condition, and makes a work atmosphere that can advance effectiveness and efficiency.
- Endeavors ought to likewise be intended at work advancement for the staff in the different frameworks, and greater open door for basic leadership ought to be given to administrators.

A. Suggestions

- The proposals for further research on the ramifications of sufficient impetuses for boosting specialist's efficiency in an association in down to earth terms could be made more show for the accompanying reasons.
- The augmentation of this review to every one of the banks in Bangladesh subsequently utilizing a bigger example to check whether it will imitate the discoveries of this review.
- A near investigation of those comparative association representatives as far as deciding the ramifications of satisfactory inspiration on laborers in connection to different indicators.
- Completing a comparable review to this, utilizing other remote claimed association to see if comparable outcomes will be gotten.

References

- [1] Kang, Y. J., Kim, S. E., & Chang, G. W. (2008). The impact of knowledge sharing on work performance: An empirical analysis of the public employees' perceptions in South Korea. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 31(14), 1548-1568.
- [2] Bowman, A. (1996). The relationship between organizational work practices and employee development. 1-51.
- [3] Chan, S. W., Heng, Y. P., Khor, S. C., Tan, W., & Yeoh, S. T. (2011). A study of employee retention in Malaysia: bank industry. Unpublished degree's thesis, University of Tunku Abdul Rahman, Kampar, Perak, Malaysia.
- [4] Ghuslan, M. I. B., Muhammad, J., & Abidin, S. Z. (2010). Factors affecting commercial bank lending practices in the Malaysian farm sector. *Journal of Public Finance*, 8(4), 39-57.
- [5] Hassan, A. (2007). Human resource development and organizational values. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 31(6), 435-448.
- [6] Herzberg, F. W., & Snyderman, B. (1957). *The motivation to work*. Wiley, New York.
- [7] Alexandru., & Silviu, T. (2010). Influence of human resources investments upon public administration. *Young Economists Journal*, 8(14), 75-82.
- [8] Kang, Y. J., Kim, S. E., & Chang, G. W. (2008). The impact of knowledge sharing on work performance: An empirical analysis of the public employees' perceptions in South Korea. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 31(14), 1548-1568.
- [9] Vigoda, G. E. (2007). Leadership style, organizational politics, and employees' performance: An empirical examination of two competing models. *Personnel Review*, 36(5), 661-683
- [10] Wang, H., Law, K. S., Hackett, R. D., Wang, D., & Chen, Z. X. (2005). Leader-member exchange as a mediator of the relationship between transformational leadership and followers' performance and organizational citizenship behavior. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48, 420-32.
- [11] White, C. (2003). Coping resources, coping responses and employee's contextual performance in a merger context. *Coping and Performance*.
- [12] Nikandrou, I., Papalexandris, N., & Bourantas, D. (2000). Gaining employee trust after acquisition: Implications for managerial action. *Employee Relations*, 22(4), 334-355.
- [13] Dissanayake, D. M. R., Wastantha, H. L. N., & Jinadasa, M. P. K. (2017). The Role of Organizational Creativity towards Innovations: A Conceptual Review on Services Sector Research Directions.
- [14] Hossain, M.D.A.; Wasantha, H.L.N.; Dissanayake, D.M.R. (2017) The Impact of Celebrity worship Motives on customer Brand relationship (CBR) Behaviour towards service sector endorsed Brands.
- [15] Hossain, A. (2023). Influence of Celebrity Credibility on Perceived Brand Trust Study on Multinational Mobile Service Brand in Bangladesh. Volume 9, Issue 1, July 2023.
- [16] Hossain, M. A., Hossen, M. S., Ahad, A., & Wasantha, H. N. Investigative Study on Celebrity Worship Motives on Customer-Brand-Relationship (CBR) Towards Tele-Communication Industry in Bangladesh. *IJFMR* Volume 6, Issue 1, January-February 2024.
- [17] Hossain, M. A., Rahman, R., Wasantha, H. L. N., Perera, G. N. R., & Khan, R. (2024). A Study to Measure the Impact of E-Marketing (Digital) Among the Customers and Firms: A Case Study of the Hilton Hotel, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 7(10), 48-62.
- [18] Bem D. J. (1967), Self-Perception, an Alternative of Cognizance Dissonance Phenomena. *Psychological Review*
- [19] Dhar R. and Werten B. K. (2000), Consumer Choice between Hedonic and Utilitarian Goods, *Journal of Marketing Research*
- [20] Festinger L. (2000), the Motivating Effects of Cognizance Dissnace in G. Lindzey (Ed). *Assessment of Human Motives*, New York Holt, 2004
- [21] Hall D. and Nougaim K. (2000), an Examination of Maslow Need Hierarchy in an Organizational Setting.
- [22] Imanyi, G. U. (2000) "A comparative study of the motivational needs of senior and middle managers in the Malaysia public service" *African Management Review* March 2000.
- [23] Kellerman B. (2007), What Every Leader Needs to Know About Followers, *Business*.
- [24] Laurie J. M. (1996) "Management and Organizational Behaviors," fourth edition pitman publishers Washington DC.
- [25] Maslow A. (1954), *Motivation and Personality*, Harper and Row New York, New York, 1954.
- [26] Maslow, A. H. (1943) *Conflict, frustration and the theory of threat*. J. Abnorm. (soc.) Psychology.
- [27] McGregor D. (1960), *the Human Side of Enterprise*, McGraw Hill Professional, 1960.
- [28] Mckenzie R. and Lee D. (1998), *Managing Through Incentives*, Oxford University Press, September 24, 1998.
- [29] Vermon, H. M. and Bedford, T., "The Absenteeism of Miners in Relation to Short-time and Other Conditions." *Industrial Health Research Board*, Report no. 62, H. M. S. O., London, 1931.
- [30] Rahman, MdSaidur, "Employee Satisfaction toward Banking Sector." *The Daily Star*, 21th January, 2011.
- [31] Rahman, M. I., Saha, S. &Gurung, H. B, Where the job satisfaction of bank employees lies: an analysis of the satisfaction factors in Bangladesh. *The Cost and Management*, *Journal of ICMA*, 34(3), 2009, pp. 1-13.
- [32] R.M. Morshador, G. D. Anupam and M. H. Syed, Job Satisfaction of Female Employees in Financial institutions of Bangladesh: A case study on selected private commercial banks in Chittagong, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, Volume 12, Issue 14, Version 1.0).
- [33] Aziri, B, Job satisfaction: A literature review. *Management research and practice*, 3(4), 2011, pp. 77-86.
- [34] Coleman, J. and Kliener, B. H, "How to Orient Employees into New Position Successfully". *Management Research News*. 22(10), 1999.
- [35] Spector, P.E, *Job Satisfaction: Application, Assessment, Causes, and Consequences*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 1997.
- [36] Rue, L., & Byars, L, *Management: Skills & Application*. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, 2003
- [37] Lease, S. H, Annual review, 1993-1997: Work attitudes and outcomes. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, Vol. 53(2): 1998, pp. 154-183.